

Multiple-front polymerization for rapid composite manufacturing

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Outline

- Motivation
- Frontal polymerization (FP)
- Multiple-front initiation
- Material and mechanical characterization
- Conclusions

Conventional bulk-cure manufacturing limitations

Boeing 37m autoclave (777X)

Heated mold for wind turbine blade

Frontal polymerization (FP) manufacturing

Frontal polymerization enables:

- Rapid curing
- Net-zero energy
- Out-of-autoclave manufacturing

Goli, et al. *J. Phys. Chem. B*, 122, 4583-4591, 2018.

Robertson, et al. *Nature*, 557, 223-227, 2018.

Dicyclopentadiene-based resin

Resin:

- *Endo*-dicyclopentadiene (*endo*-DCPD)
- Grubbs' catalyst (GC2)
- Tributylphosphite (TBP) (inhibitor)

Polymer:

- Thermally stable ($T_g = 150\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$)
- Chemically stable
- High-performance thermoset

Robertson, et al. *Nature*, 557, 223-227, 2018.

VARTM composite processing

- 12 plies Toray T300 carbon fiber 2 × 2 twill weave fabric

High-quality FP composites

30 cm × 30 cm panel fabricated in **< 5 min**

Corrugated panel

Cross-section

Robertson, et al. *Nature*, 557, 223-227, 2018.

Cure time savings via multiple-front initiation

One trigger/front FP

Two triggers/fronts FP

Through-thickness FP

- FP composites demonstrate **100x cure time** and **1,000x energy consumption savings** compared to conventional bulk-cure manufacturing
- Initiating additional fronts **further reduces cure time** and offers avenue for larger scale manufacturing

In-situ thermal infrared imaging for different trigger configurations

Modeling two-fronts initiation in neat resin

Test setup

Experiment: *in-situ* thermal infrared imaging

Simulation: temperature (θ) and degree of cure (α) profiles over time

- Thermal overshoot where two fronts merge captured via simulation
- Excessive overshoot may lead to material degradation

Mechanical characterization

Control specimen:

- Bisphenol A (BPA) aerospace-grade epoxy (Araldite® LY 8605 / Aradur® 8605)
- Conventional bulk-cured DCPD

Control specimen temperature profiles

ASTM standard D3039 tensile tests

- One-front FP composite properties comparable to both conventional cure systems
- Need to determine two-front FP composite properties

Summary

- FP is a promising curing strategy for rapid, energy-efficient composite manufacturing
- Multiple front initiation is an avenue for further reducing cure times and larger scale manufacturing
- Necessary to determine effect of thermal overshoot in two-fronts FP sample on mechanical properties

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